

DCH Field Data Storage Guidelines

Version 1.0.0

1. Keep three instances
2. Keep two local instances on different media
3. Keep one off-site copy
4. Automatize data replication and backup
5. Document procedure and responsibilities

1 Three instances

Keep three instances of the data. Besides the original working instance, keep two copies of your project data.

2 Two local instances on different media

Use dust- and waterproof storage media (at least protected according to [IP55](#), better [IP67](#)) for the local copy and the off-site copy, if the latter is not internet-based.

3 One off-site copy

If your field situation does not allow for an internet-based off-site copy, keep one copy as removed from the other copies as possible. This can mean keeping it in a separate bag or a separate room.

4 Automatize data replication and backup

The process of regular local replication and off-site backup should be as regular as possible, and automatized if possible. The frequency of replication and backup must be adjusted to the maximum acceptable amount of data loss in case of an incident.

5 Document procedure and responsibilities

Document the data storage procedure – including location of the three copies, frequency of replication and backup – as well as the responsibilities for implementing the procedure e.g. in your data management plan.